

1 **Shc3 and Sh-binding chemistry in embryonic development.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of a set
9 of Shc3 and Sh-binding molecules with functions in lineage commitment in embryonic stem cells of the
10 human embryo. Genes engaged included Stac, Sh3bp5, Sh2bp3 and Stap2.

11 Citations

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